

In 2024, the PANDORA project made significant strides in its objectives. Notable achievements include the establishment of the framework's architecture, the advancement of pilot activities, and further progress in research. These efforts were complemented by fostering collaborations with various initiatives and active participation in prominent European events, further enhancing the project's impact.

News

Interview with the Scientific Coordinator Dr. Georgios Bouloukakis

Dr. Georgios Bouloukakis, Associate Professor at Institut Mines-Télécom (IMT), explains PANDORA'S mission to develop trustworthy AI solutions in the cloud-edge continuum.

[Read more..](#)

Interview with Deputy Coordinator Dr. Konstantinos Tserpes

In this interview, Konstantinos Tserpes, Deputy Coordinator of the PANDORA project and a faculty member at the National Technical University of Athens, provides an overview of the project's goals and NTUA's role in the development of the project....

[Read more](#)

FLEdge: Benchmarking Federated Learning Applications in Edge Computing Systems

Published in the 25th International Middleware Conference (MIDDLEWARE '24). This paper introduces FLEdge, a hardware-centric framework for benchmarking Federated Learning (FL) on edge computing systems, addressing key challenges like: ♦ Hardware diversity and memory bottlenecks ♦ Network conditions' impact on...

[Read more...](#)

MESS+: Energy-Optimal Inferencing in Language Model Zoos with Service Level Guarantees

Authors: Ryan Zhang (Harvard Greeley High School), Herbert Woitschläger (Technical University of Munich), Shiqiang Wang (IBM Research), Hans-Arno Jacobsen (University of Toronto).

MESS+: Energy-Optimal Inferencing in Language Model Zoos with Service Level Guarantees

A novel approach for energy-optimal model selection in large language model (LLM) zoos with Service Level Agreements (SLAs). Published in the NeurIPS 2024 Workshop on Adaptive Foundation Models, this paper demonstrates how MESS+ enables: ♦ Energy-efficient inferencing while maintaining...

[Read more...](#)

Events

Efficient and Trustworthy AI in the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum | DataWeek24

Dr. Georgios Bouloukakis, our Technical Coordinator from IMTfrance, presented the PANDORA project during the session: Efficient and Trustworthy AI in the Edge-to-Cloud Continuum at the DataWeek24. The session, part of Manufacturing...

[Read more...](#)

Achieving efficient trustworthy AI in the cloud-edge continuum – AI Data Robotics Forum

On November 4th, PANDORA co-organized the workshop "Achieving Efficient and Trustworthy AI in the Cloud-Edge Continuum" alongside AI-DAPT, EXTRA-BRAIN, MANOLO, and RAIDO at the AI, Data, and Robotics Forum (ADRF)...

[Read more...](#)

2nd Plenary Meeting – Novi Sad

On October 17–18, 2024, the PANDORA consortium gathered at the University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Sciences, for a dynamic Plenary Meeting. This inspiring two-day event brought together partners from...

[Read more...](#)

Mathematical Methods for Explainable AI

On October 14, 2024, PANDORA participated in the "Mathematical Methods for Explainable AI" workshop, hosted by Siemens at the TUM Garching Campus in Munich, Germany. Georgios Bouloukakis, PANDORA's scientific project...

[Read more...](#)

Participation in European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2024

Moving to the Edge: The Impact and Implications of the CEI Continuum on Manufacturing This session delves into the growing significance of bringing AI to the edge and its transformative...

[Read more...](#)

Distributed & Continual Inference & Learning – IEEE MLSP 2024

AARHUS University in collaboration with PANDORA and NordForsk NUI coorganized a special session in the IEEE MLSP 2024 titled "Distributed and Continual Inference and Learning". Chaired by Prof. Alexandros Iosifidis, this...

[Read more...](#)

[Unsubscribe](#) | [Manage your subscription](#) | [View online](#)

This project has received funding from the EUROPEAN COMMUNICATIONS NETWORKS, CONTENT and TECHNOLOGY (CNECT) program under Grant Agreement No 101135775 (PANDORA project). This document reflects only the author's view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains